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CULTiVATE

Policy brief: inclusive, participatory and resilient sustainable UPU food sharing scenario planning - D6.2

WP 6, T 6.2.3

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Executive Summary

Cities are becoming critical spaces for responding to climate, social, and food system challenges. **Food sharing initiatives provide environmental and social benefits**—from reducing waste to strengthening community resilience—but questions persist about **how they can scale, adapt, and amplify their positive impacts**, particularly in rapidly changing and uncertain conditions.

This policy brief presents **futures thinking as a practical way to address these challenges**. Scenario planning, in particular, offers a structured method for exploring uncertainty, stress-testing ideas, and co-creating shared visions for action. When designed and implemented inclusively, these processes help surface diverse perspectives, reveal tensions, and strengthen collaboration across public authorities, civil society, and private actors. **The result is greater preparedness, adaptability, and long-term strategic alignment** within urban food governance.

Drawing on workshops held in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht as part of the Horizon Europe CULTIVATE project, **this brief outlines key lessons and actionable recommendations for embedding scenario planning into food governance**. The guidance covers four interconnected areas: workshop preparation and relevance, participant selection and inclusion, facilitation, and pathways to translate outputs into policy and practice. Practical examples demonstrate how these approaches have been applied in real contexts.

By integrating futures thinking into urban food governance, decision-makers and practitioners can expand the benefits of food sharing initiatives, strengthen resilience, and **support more just and sustainable urban food systems**.

What is CULTIVATE?

CULTIVATE is a four-year Innovation Action funded by the EU Horizon Europe (GA No. 101083377) designed to support sustainable urban and peri-urban (UPU) food sharing and help transform urban food systems towards more just and sustainable. CULTIVATE will co-design a ground-breaking online social innovation support platform – The Food Sharing Compass – with food sharing initiatives (FSIs), local authorities, food supply actors, researchers and citizens in order to: map, track and monitor UPU food sharing landscapes; identify the costs, benefits and impacts of FSIs; help actors navigate governance architectures and ensure appropriate policies and regulations of food sharing; support increased citizen engagement in UPU food sharing; and create a community of practice for FSIs. Working collaboratively with multiple actors, CULTIVATE will develop more sustainable, resilient and healthy UPU food systems supporting inclusive climate mitigation and adaptation ambitions of the EU.

Using Futures Thinking to Expand the Benefits of Food Sharing Initiatives

Urban food systems are under increasing strain from accelerating ecological crises and widening social inequalities, making **cities key arenas for driving sustainable transformations**^[1]. In this context, **food sharing initiatives have expanded across urban and peri-urban areas**, bringing people together to grow, cook, redistribute, and share food, skills, and resources, and **offering recognised social and environmental benefits**^[2,3]. However, these initiatives face several structural barriers—including fragmented governance, insufficient stable funding, unequal participation, and limited integration into policy agendas—that constrain their ability to scale and deepen their impact^[4]. As a result, significant questions remain about **how they can scale, adapt, multiply and sustain their positive contributions** amid rising economic and political uncertainties and systemic disruptions—highlighting a clear need for policy approaches that better support and strengthen their role in food transitions.

Futures thinking—or *futuring*—offers creative and systematic tools to navigate these challenges and imagine transformative pathways, and is increasingly recognised as valuable for exploring alternative futures and supporting sustainability transitions^[5,6,7]. Among the futuring approaches, **scenario planning** has proven especially effective for developing participatory strategies toward more sustainable futures^[8], bringing diverse actors together to explore possible trajectories, surface tensions, and co-create shared visions of inclusive and resilient food systems. By weaving multiple perspectives into long-term thinking, scenario planning exercises help policymakers and other food sharing practitioners anticipate challenges, identify adaptive strategies, and strengthen their capacity to deliver positive impacts—building the **reflexivity, adaptability, and inclusiveness** essential for just and resilient food systems.

As part of the **Horizon Europe-funded CULTIVATE project**, we developed a series of **inclusive and participatory food-sharing scenario planning workshops** in the three project hub cities, where tools and analyses were developed for further replication across Europe: **Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht**. We brought together diverse food sharing actors - policymakers, private sector actors and civil society organisations- to reflect, plan, and drive systemic change by exploring how urban and peri-urban food sharing can foster fairer and more sustainable food futures. Using participatory scenario planning, participants co-created shared visions and pathways for sustainable urban food sharing and tested these plans against exploratory future scenarios (see Images 1, 2 and 3).

This policy brief presents key recommendations for policymakers and other food sharing practitioners seeking to strengthen the role of food sharing in sustainable urban transitions. It offers guidance on designing and integrating scenario planning approaches into food governance processes, such as urban food policies.

Images 1–3: Scenario planning workshops conducted in Utrecht, Barcelona, and Milan.

Recommendations for Developing Inclusive, Participatory, Resilient and Impactful Sustainable Future Scenario Planning Workshops

The recommendations below offer **practical ways to make scenario planning more inclusive, participatory, and resilient**, while maximising the impact of urban food sharing. Each set of recommendations is illustrated with a practical example from the CULTIVATE project, showing how this approach can be applied in specific contexts.

A detailed description of how to apply scenario planning, step-by-step guidance, and practical examples can be found in the [Guidebook on Inclusive, Participatory, and Resilient Sustainable Urban Food Sharing Scenario Planning](#).

Workshop Preparation and Relevance

- **Ensure contextual relevance:** Select a workshop topic that is meaningful for your local context by consulting key actors to understand their priorities and needs. Collaboratively agree on the topic to increase engagement, usefulness, and impact.
- **Acknowledge trade-offs or tensions:** Consider the conflicts inherent in food system transitions, for example, recognising the possibility of differing or competing perspectives or goals among actors. Being explicit about these differences allows participants to engage more honestly, surface underlying concerns, and work toward more realistic, robust, and widely supported strategies.
- **Value diverse knowledge:** Including and valuing different kinds of expertise—both scientific, regulatory and knowledge gained through practice or experience—is essential for understanding complex systems and making well-informed decisions. Recognising all perspectives ensures that technical insights and lived experiences meaningfully inform outcomes, uncovering challenges and opportunities that might otherwise be missed.
- **Ensure transparency:** Clearly communicate objectives, process, and expected outputs.

Examples from implementing the CULTIVATE workshops:

To clarify diverging underlying concerns, during the Barcelona workshop on food waste and redistribution issues, organisers and participants openly acknowledged underlying tensions. These centred on the trade-off between expanding food redistribution to reduce waste and address food insecurity, and prioritising measures that prevent food waste at its source.

Participant Selection and Engagement

- **Promote diversity:** Engage a wide range of food system actors—from public, private, and civil society sectors—and across diverse socio-demographic and economic backgrounds (gender, age, etc.). If including vulnerable groups, avoid tokenistic inclusion by engaging early and meaningfully.
- **Address accessibility barriers:** Address any financial, linguistic, mobility, digital, or caregiving barriers that may prevent participation.
- **Provide support:** Offer logistical support, background materials, and interpretation services to ensure meaningful engagement.
- **Create safe and trusting spaces:** Establish clear ground rules and foster environments conducive to honest and respectful dialogue.

Examples from implementing the CULTIVATE workshops:

In the workshops held in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht, to promote diversity, organisers worked closely with representatives from relevant organisations to refine and expand their initial lists of potential participants, ensuring a more comprehensive mapping of key actors. For example, the Municipal Food Policy Office of Milan played an active role by reviewing the participant list and suggesting additional actors, thereby broadening inclusion and strengthening the diversity of perspectives.

Workshop Facilitation

- **Manage power dynamics:** Use facilitation techniques to balance participation and surface inequities. This helps ensure that no single actor or perspective dominates the process, enabling more inclusive dialogue and more equitable co-creation of future pathways.
- **Employ diverse engagement formats:** Alternate between individual reflection, small-group discussion, and plenary sessions to ensure all voices are heard.
- **Provide accessible visual information:** Accessible tools and outputs (e.g., roadmaps, illustrations and graphic templates) support actors' deliberation and engagement and enhance impact and results.
- **Ensure accountability:** Clearly communicate the influence of workshop outcomes and follow up with concrete actions.

Examples from implementing the CULTIVATE workshops:

In Barcelona, to provide accessible visual information, organisers brought an illustrator on board to capture the workshop's key insights through a creative mix of drawings and text. To spark engagement and inspire imagination in future sessions, the illustrator also designed tarot-inspired scenario planning cards (see Image 4), turning complex ideas into visually compelling tools that encourage participants to explore possibilities in a playful and thought-provoking way.

Image 4: Tarot-inspired scenario planning cards

Translating Outputs into Policy and Practice

- **Build capacity throughout the process:** Strengthen participants' ability to apply and adapt scenario methodologies and associated outputs across different policy and practice arenas, including the shared vision and narratives. This includes using them beyond food policy domains and at other scales, both within and beyond the public sector. To do this, generating diverse outputs through the process can be beneficial (such as visuals, decalogues, guides or other communicative materials), as well as making the most of connections created across actors through the workshops and beyond. These efforts enable participants to apply workshop insights in concrete decision-making processes across sectors or administrations, or to link issues that are often treated separately, such as justice and sustainability.
- **Allocate time for relationship-building.** Beyond scenario planning, workshops serve as networking platforms where diverse actors connected by a shared theme can engage in dialogue, explore the future of the food sharing landscape, and foster lasting relationships. Leaving space to cultivate relations is especially relevant, as time constraints often limit opportunities for meaningful interactions between organisations and the public and private

sectors. These spaces also provide a chance to build relationships that help navigate the trade-offs and differing priorities in food transitions, while fostering inclusivity by bringing together diverse perspectives.

- **Integrate into policy:** Ensure workshop outcomes are linked to local policy agendas and formally recognised strategies by bringing them into relevant consultation processes, presenting them in strategic forums, and using them to inform or spur policy changes. This increases the likelihood that workshop insights meaningfully shape decision-making and lead to concrete implementation.
- **Disseminate results through targeted sharing.** Share workshop outputs to ensure they inform formal strategies and policies—for example, through targeted sharing to key actors or networks, converting outputs into guides or principles, or presenting them to relevant working groups and meetings on related topics. Identify the most strategic audiences for dissemination, and consider not only local recipients but also how the results could inform and strengthen governance processes at other scales and different geographies.
- **Track impact:** Keep participants informed about how their contributions are used and the resulting decisions or policy changes, showing that their engagement in these processes makes a meaningful impact. This is essential to prevent participant fatigue and ensure that workshop insights are carried forward into ongoing or new processes, avoiding the loss of time, resources, and collective effort.

Examples from implementing the CULTIVATE workshops:

After Milan’s workshops, the City Council considered adopting the methodology to develop the municipal plan to improve air quality and environmental conditions. In Barcelona, workshop outcomes were shared with the Food Waste Working Group of the Barcelona Food Council and incorporated into the process of developing the city’s food waste diagnosis. To support wider dissemination, the organisers co-created the *Decalogue on Food Waste and the Right to Food* as part of the CULTIVATE project, translating workshop discussions into a clear set of guiding principles for policymakers and food-sharing practitioners. All outcomes align with the Barcelona Healthy and Sustainable Food Strategy 2030.

Additional resources

- [Policy Brief on Urban and Peri-Urban Food Sharing Governance](#) - This policy brief outlines the key governance barriers that currently constrain the sustainability potential of food sharing and presents a set of high-level policy recommendations to address them.
- [Guidebook on Inclusive, Participatory, and Resilient Sustainable Urban Food Sharing Scenario Planning](#) - This guide provides practical tools for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to apply futures thinking to urban food systems, helping cities navigate environmental, social, and governance challenges.
- [The Menu of Good Governance](#) - A novel, dynamic and interactive online decision support tool for policymakers and other actors who develop and implement policies and projects on food sharing.

For additional resources to strengthen food sharing, visit <https://cultivate-project.eu/>

Do you want to find out more?

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